

Fluorimetric determination of dopamine via its derivatization with 1,2-phenylenediamine

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A simple, rapid and sensitive fluorimetric method for the determination of dopamine is developed. It is based on the chemical reaction of quinone of dopamine hydrochloride (produced *in situ* from dopamine hydrochloride in presence of oxygen and alkali) with 1,2-phenylene diamine (OPDA) in alcoholic medium under alkaline condition at RT. The reaction leads to a fluorescent product and the effects of organic solvents on fluorescence spectra were examined and discussed. Among the common organic solvents tested, methanol was selected because of its efficient sensitizing capability. Effects of pH, temperature, reaction time and the foreign ions on the determination of dopamine have been examined. The behavior of dopamine in acid-base medium was studied both by spectrofluorimetry and spectrophotometry. The fluorescence intensity was measured at λ_{em} 530 nm (λ_{ex} 450 nm). Under optimum condition a linear relationship was obtained between the relative fluorescence intensity and concentration of dopamine in the concentration range of 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ to 6.6×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ of dopamine. The linear regression equation of the calibration graph is F.I. = $1.376 \times C$ (mol dm⁻³) + 4.112, with a correlation coefficient of 0.9921. The limit of detection is 2.114×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³, which is obviously lower than the other fluorimetric methods reported.

To understand the functions and interactions between even simple networks of neurons, a complete knowledge of the neurotransmitters and neuromodulatory agents used within each neuron in the network, is required. The simultaneous detection and quantification of neurotransmitters, metabolites and co-factors at the level of individual neurons provide background and fundamental information for neurophysiology. Although there are hundreds of transmitters, the indolamines such as 5-hydroxytryptamine (serotonin) and the catecholamines (dopamine, epinephrine, octopamine, etc.) are of particular interest because of their widespread distribution in central and peripheral tissues, broad spectrum of biological action, and critical roles in diverse pathologies¹. While the mapping of indolamine and catecholamine (CA) containing neurons in invertebrate central nervous system (CNS) reveals a number of identified cells², only a few have been characterized biochemically³. In general, past assays have generally been cell-system specific and often dependent on highly molecule-specific (e.g. enzymatic) detection methods. Thus a considerable effort has been devoted to the development of improved analytical methods for generally applicable multi-component quantitative single-cell assays.

Catecholamine (CA) drugs are aromatic vicinal-diols those consist of amines attached to a benzene ring bearing

two hydroxyl groups (catechol). The catecholamines are primarily synthesized in vesicles of the chromaffin cells in the adrenal medulla. The drugs are now widely used in the treatment of bronchial asthma, hypertension, Parkinson's diseases (PD), drug abuse, schizophrenia and myocardial infarction and cardiac surgery. On the other hand, dopamine a neurotransmitter, is one of the naturally occurring catecholamines and its hydrochloride salt has been used in the treatment of acute congestive and renal failures associated with shock episodes⁴. Many analytical chemists try to find compendious methods for the determination of dopamine in authentic and dosage forms. Now it is believed that dopamine deficiency causes the basal ganglia of human brain. Dopamine is a neurotransmitter, a chemical messenger in the mammalian nervous system. In PD the neural cell that produces dopamine deteriorates. When these neurons start to disappear, the normal rate of dopamine production decrease. It was discovered that when dopamine supply is abnormally low, Parkinson's symptoms start to appear. Next to PD's primary symptoms mentioned above, a patient might also start to suffer from secondary symptoms, which include : depression, senility, postural deformity, and difficulty in speaking. The catecholamines (CAs) are present in relatively large amounts in drugs and many efforts have been made to develop rapid, simple and accurate analytical procedures

for their determination. Pharmaceutical preparations containing these are available for many years and several analytical procedures have been proposed for their control.

Many methods have been proposed for the determination of catecholamines (CAs) and their metabolites, such as HPLC with electrochemical detection⁵⁻⁷. However, most of the methods needed complicated sample pre-treatment or did not have the required sensitivity. Nohta *et al.* reported an HPLC-fluorimetric method for the simultaneous detection of CAs and their related compounds with a post column technique utilizing coulometric oxidation followed by fluorescence derivatization with 1,2-diphenylethylenediamine⁶. However the reported method needed a tedious sample pre-treatment step. Also to quantify CAs and their metabolites, at least 700 μL of plasma sample was required.

The other well-known methods described in the literature for dopamine determination in biological samples and pharmaceutical formulations involve spectrophotometry⁸ spectrofluorimetry⁹, gas¹⁰ and liquid chromatography¹¹ and amperometry¹². But most of these detection methods do lend themselves to miniaturization. Other common methods like stopped-flow technique¹³ and flow injection analysis (FIA)¹⁴ were reported earlier but the errors in the quantification were critical due to the interference of other compounds present in the samples.

A new one step fluorimetric method for the quantification of dopamine based on its chemical reaction (via the formation of its quinone derivative in presence of oxygen and alkali) with OPDA (1,2-phenylenediamine) in methanolic medium has been reported here. The fluorescent intensity of the product at λ_{em} 530 nm (λ_{ex} 450 nm) is a direct measure of dopamine concentration. The method described here is very quick, reliable, simple and does not need any extraction step. Other common CAs like epinephrine (E), norepinephrine (NE), octopamine which are commonly present with dopamine in the central and peripheral tissues do not respond to the reaction under the proposed reaction condition.

Results and discussion

Characteristics of dopamine and OPDA :

In alkaline medium catecholamine (CAs) solutions are hydrolyzed and oxidized by atmospheric oxygen giving yellow-brownish coloration due to aminochrome derivatives¹⁵. These compounds are very much unstable. Some spectrophotometric methods used the high reactivity of the aminochrome in order to give coupling reactions with another reagent¹⁶. Dopamine bears two adjacent hydroxyl groups in the phenyl ring that makes it unstable even when

it is dissolved in water as dopamine hydrochloride salt. Diffuse sunlight even catalyzes the oxidation of dopamine and direct sunlight causes much damage. This is simply authenticated by the appearance of reddish coloration of the dopamine hydrochloride solution. In all cases, dopamine oxidation¹⁷ took place, generating the corresponding *o*-quinone. Again, catechol and the quinone showed their susceptibility towards oxidation due to the resonance in the aromatic ring, that makes the oxidation favorable and this behavior is pronounced for *ortho* and *para* derivatives. Hence dopamine hydrochloride solution was always kept in an air-tight container in the dark (covered with black paper) at a temp. $\sim 4^\circ$. However, it remains stable in alcohol for months together. Again, 1,2-phenylene diamine is also an unstable compound under ambient condition and turns yellow and then black. So it was also stored in the similar fashion as was done for dopamine hydrochloride.

The alcoholic solutions of the two compounds i.e. dopamine hydrochloride and OPDA individually did not show any native fluorescence from the respective methanolic solutions. No fluorescence was developed with they were treated separately with methanolic solution of KOH. However, strong fluorescence (λ_{em} 530 nm; λ_{ex} 450 nm) was noticed when these two reagents were mixed together in methanolic KOH solution.

The structure of the reagents and the possible reaction products are shown in Fig. 1. It was assumed that the final reaction product was formed via the coupling of quinone of dopamine hydrochloride (produced *in situ* from dopamine hydrochloride in presence of oxygen and alkali) and OPDA.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation for the structure of the reagents and the reaction product.

The formation of the new fluorescence product was further confirmed from capillary zone electrophoresis studies using a Lambda 1010 instrument attached to a UV detector (PRINCE Autosampler, 2-Lift model, Netherlands) operating at 20 kV with a current strength 13 μA .

Excitation and emission spectra :

It was seen that the suitable excitation and emission maximum for the reaction product were at 450 and 530 nm, respectively, in methanol. Among the various solvents (methanol, ethanol and DMF) tested, methanol was selected

as the most suitable reagent for the determination of dopamine. Again, the fluorescence intensity of the product was maximum in methanol compared to other solvents. The fluorescence spectra of the product and the reagent blank (containing no dopamine) are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Fluorescence emission (A) spectra (after blank subtraction) of the product in methanol. Curve B shows the emission spectra of the blank (containing no OPDA solution). Conditions: Concentration of dopamine in the solution was 5.4×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} .

Effects of the reaction variables :

Influence of potassium hydroxide :

Effect of addition of KOH (saturated in methanol) on the relative fluorescence intensity of dopamine in methanol has been studied. The reaction mixture did not show any fluorescence in the absence of KOH. In presence of KOH the reaction mixture showed strong fluorescence. So KOH solution has a vital role to play for the reaction between dopamine and OPDA and hence on the fluorescence of the reaction product. Keeping the other reagent concentration same, varying amounts of KOH (saturated in methanol) solution (ranging from 10 μl to 100 μl) was added to the reaction mixture (3 ml volume in each case). The fluorescence intensity was found to be maximum with 40 μl of KOH solution (leading to final pH ~6–7). Addition of additional volume of KOH raised the pH of the medium (leading to final pH ~8) whereas the fluorescence intensity remained virtually constant and a blue shifting of the emission peak was observed. The results were shown in Fig. 3. So 40 μl solution of saturated potassium hydroxide (pH ~6–7) was chosen as a suitable aliquot for the reaction to occur. Once the fluorescent product is formed, the fluorescence intensity of the product did not change notably in acidic (dil. H_2SO_4) environment. The reaction was also carried

Fig. 3. Influence of the addition of potassium hydroxide concentration. Condition: Concentration of dopamine in the solution was 3.3×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} .

out with Na_2CO_3 solution in place of KOH solution. But it did not help the reaction to proceed in a better way.

Effect of solvent on the emission wavelength of dopamine :

Investigations were made to study the effect of organic solvent on the relative fluorescence intensity of the reaction product. Among the organic solvents tested, methanol has been found to be the best. Intense and reproducible fluorescence was observed for the product in methanol. The other solvents tested were ethanol and DMF. The effects of DMF and ethanol on the emission wavelength of the product were similar to that of methanol. But the λ_{em} was shifted to shorter wavelength (blue shift) region in case of ethanol and to longer wavelength in case of DMF. DMF is a hydrogen bond acceptor and presumably it helps in strengthening conjugation between the isolated double electrons of oxygen atom and the benzene ring. So DMF can increase the intramolecular conjugation of the reaction product. Therefore, DMF showed the red shifting¹⁸ of the emission peak for the product. The reaction between dopamine and OPDA in dry DMF as solvent did not give satisfactory reaction product like methanol. In DMF the fluorescence intensity of the reagent itself was very large causing a large blank value. Ethanol is a donor of hydrogen bond and its effect could not be ascertained and further research is warranted.

Effect of time :

Keeping all other parameters unaltered, time dependent fluorescence intensity of the mixtures containing 5×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} and 5×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} of dopamine were tested. It was found that the change of fluorescence intensity increases gradually with time and that is shown in Fig. 4. The maximum fluorescence intensity was observed after keeping the mixture for ~4 h and after that it remained vir-

tually constant for days together. The results showed that the relative fluorescence intensity of the product remained stable for at least 30 h when kept in a refrigerator at $\sim 4^\circ$ in an airtight container.

Fig. 4. Effect of standing time on the fluorescence intensity (at λ_{em} : 530 nm) of the product. Condition: Concentration of dopamine in set A: 0.5×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} . Concentration of dopamine in set B: 0.5×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} .

Effect of temperature :

Once the product is formed, the fluorescence intensity of the product was measured at different temperatures in the reaction medium. The temperature dependent study in the range of 25° to 60° showed drastic lowering of the fluorescence intensity of the product at higher temperature. The lowered fluorescence intensity might be due to the possible degradation of the product. Therefore the reaction and the subsequent measurements were done at room temperature (25°).

Sequence of addition :

The methanolic solution of dopamine hydrochloride remained stable under ambient condition. But aqueous solution of dopamine hydrochloride at normal pH and in alkaline pH turned pink even after an hour on standing. Alkaline solution is more susceptible to oxidation. Development of pink color is faster in the presence of catalytic amount of preformed *o*-quinone. Trace of *o*-quinone is readily formed from dopamine hydrochloride solution for always due to the addition of KOH. It has been said that trace of *o*-quinone might help the reaction to take place between dopamine and OPDA. This was indirectly confirmed by changing the sequence of addition of KOH and OPDA, as described in the procedure. That is why KOH was introduced before the addition of OPDA.

Calibration graph of dopamine and analytical parameters :

Under the selected reaction condition, a linear relation-

ship was obtained between the fluorescence intensity and the concentration of dopamine in the range of 1×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} to 6.6×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} of dopamine. The fluorescence intensities were obtained after subtracting the blank. The linear regression equation of calibration graph is, $F.I. = 1.376 \times C$ (mol dm^{-3}) + 4.112, with a correlation coefficient of 0.9921. The standard deviation of 8 blank measurements is 0.9697 and the limit of detection (LOD) is 2.114×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} (calculated as $LOD = 3 S_B/m$, where S_B = standard deviation of the blank and m = slope of the calibration graph).

UV-adsorption study of dopamine :

The acid-base behavior of dopamine :

Freshly prepared methanolic solution of dopamine hydrochloride showed a λ_{max} at 280 nm in the experimental concentration range. Whereas, 1,2-phenylene diamine (OPDA) has maximum absorption at 188 nm. The acid-base behavior of dopamine was investigated in detail using UV-spectroscopy and the relative absorption spectra of dopamine at different pH are shown in Fig. 5. It was ob-

Fig. 5. Absorption spectra of 3.1×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} dopamine hydrochloride at different pH. Condition: pH: 5.07 (curve a); 3.1 (curve b); 1.23 (curve c); 7.5 (curve d); 9.37 (curve e); 10.82 (curve f); 11.92 (curve g).

served that in the relative absorbance of dopamine there was no noticeable change in acidic medium but in alkaline medium absorbance increases with the rise in pH and attains a maximum at pH 11.92 which is shown in Fig. 6.

It was also observed that the λ_{max} of dopamine was located at ~ 280 nm (curves a to c) when pH was below 7.5. With the rise in pH value of the solution above 7.5, the λ_{max} of dopamine shifted to 290 nm (curve d) and then again slowly shifted to the more red region. At pH 11.92, the λ_{max} becomes located at 304 nm (curve g). So it is clear from the UV-visible spectral shifts of λ_{max} that dopamine on deprotonation showed the first red shifting (~ 10 nm) due to phenoxide ions. The second red shifting indicates oxida-

Fig. 6. Effect of pH on the absorption spectra of dopamine. Condition : The concentration of dopamine was 3.1×10^{-5} mol dm $^{-3}$ and λ_{\max} varies from 280 nm –304 nm.

tion of dopamine in the higher pH condition as mentioned earlier. However, it was seen that there is no enhancement of fluorescence intensity for the fluorescing product of dopamine when the pH value goes above 7.5. There was some quenching of fluorescence intensity in strong alkaline medium. So the optimum pH for the fluorescence study was maintained around ~6–7.

Fig. 7

It is well known that *o*- and *p*-dihydroxy benzene can easily be oxidized to their corresponding quinones¹⁹ in strong alkaline solution and in the presence of air. So obviously, 280–283 nm is the λ_{\max} of dopamine in acidic solution (below pH 7). But in an alkaline solution, dopamine is oxidized by oxygen in air to form an oxidation product. The rate of oxidation could somehow be retarded in the nitrogen atmosphere. The 295–304 nm peak is the λ_{\max} of the oxidation product i.e. due to quinone. The λ_{\max} of the oxidation product is calculated as follows according to Woodward rule²⁰ (numbers in bracket indicate number of carbon atom of product molecule) : Base value, 215 nm; one conjugated double bond (6), add 30 nm; one homoannular diene, add 39 nm; two double bond outside the ring (1,6), add 10 nm, one alkyl (3), add 12 nm; solvent is methanol so subtract 0 nm; total is 306 nm. The measured value (304 nm) agreed with calculated value (306 nm) for the λ_{\max} of the oxidation product. It should be noted that the λ_{\max} of the oxidation product falls in the longer wavelength region than that of dopamine, this is due to the increased conjugation in the oxidation product. So obviously the oxidation product is non-fluorescing substance

due to its benzoquinonyl structure.

Interference study :

To examine the selectivity of the method, a brief investigation was made with the possible interfering substances like epinephrine (E), norepinephrine (NE), octopamine, metanephrine, 3-methoxy tyramine, 4-methoxy tyramine. But none of them interfered with the dopamine determination while present in equal amount though they have dopamine like structure.

Experimental

Reagents :

The reagent dopamine hydrochloride (Sigma was used as received and OPDA (Aldrich was used after recrystallisation from alcohol. Epinephrine (E), norepinephrine (NE), octopamine, metanephrine, 3-methoxy tyramine, 4-methoxy tyramine were purchased from Sigma. Pure methanol was purchased from S.D. Fine chemicals and potassium hydroxide was purchased from Sisco, Mumbai, India. A stock solution of OPDA and dopamine (both of 10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$) were prepared in methanol. From this stock solution lower dilutions (10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$, 10^{-5} mol dm $^{-3}$, 10^{-6} mol dm $^{-3}$) were prepared by proper dilution using alcohol. Potassium hydroxide solution (saturated) was prepared in methanol. Double-distilled water was used throughout the course of work. All solutions were stored at 4° in the dark.

Instruments :

All the fluorescence spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer LS-50B spectrofluorimeter equipped with a 9.9 W xenon flash lamp and a photo multiplier tube with S-20 spectral response. The spectrofluorimeter was linked to a personal computer and utilized the Perkin-Elmer FLDM software package for data collection and processing. All reactions were carried out in well-stoppered quartz cuvette. A digital pH meter (ECL, Government of India) was used for pH measurement throughout the whole experiment. Capillary zone electrophoresis study was done using a Lambda 1010 instrument attached to a UV detector (PRINCE Autosampler, 2-Lift model, Netherlands) operating at 20 kV with a current strength 13 μ A.

Procedure :

Varying amounts (ranging from 3 μ l to 300 μ l) of stock dopamine hydrochloride solutions (10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$) were placed into a series of standard quartz cuvettes. In each cuvette 40 μ l of saturated KOH solutions were added and was mixed with OPDA (10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$) solution and then varying amounts of methanol were added such that the final volumes of methanol were added such that the final

volumes of all sets were equal (3 ml) and the final dopamine concentration varied from 6.6×10^{-5} (mol dm⁻³) to 1.0×10^{-6} (mol dm⁻³). A blank solution without dopamine hydrochloride was also prepared. After that the mixtures were kept for 3–4 h for completion of the reaction and then the fluorescence intensities were measured at 530 nm (λ_{ex} 450 nm). For all measurements both the excitation and emission slits used were of 10 nm.

Conclusions :

Here has been described a fluorimetric method for dopamine determination. It is based on the new chemical reaction via the coupling of quinone of dopamine hydrochloride (produced *in situ* from dopamine hydrochloride in presence of oxygen and alkali) with 1,2-henylene diamine in alkaline methanolic medium. The reaction leads to a fluorescent product. The limit of detection is 2.114×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³, which is obviously lower than the other fluorimetric methods reported. The procedure is free from the interferences due to similar compounds. The main advantage of the proposed method is that it is simple, rapid and does not need any extraction step.

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